

Results and Discussion :

Changes in soil properties :

Table (1) shows that saline water increased soil salinity (EC) after plant harvesting in all treatments from 2.79 up to 12.69 dS/m. Values of EC for irrigated soil clearly increased with increasing salinity water used but the difference between water composition was not clear. That means, the importance effect of total water salinity of irrigation water. On the other side, table (1) disclose that values of soil reaction (pH) decreased with increasing salinity levels (e.g., from 8.16 to 7.65).

Table (1): Effect of salinity levels, salt composition of irrigation water and nitrogen fertilization on EC of soil solution (soil paste) and soil pH after wheat harvest

Treatments		EC (dS/M)					pH (1:2.5 soil suspension)				
Water quality	salinity level	N ₀	N ₁	n ₂	N ₃	Mean	N ₀	N ₁	n ₂	N ₃	Mean
W ₀	C ₀	2.79	2.81	2.71	2.84	2.79	8.14	8.17	8.18	8.17	8.16
W ₁	C ₁	7.53	7.54	7.59	7.61	7.57	7.85	7.84	7.84	7.85	7.85
	C ₂	10.33	10.35	10.28	10.36	10.33	7.73	7.73	7.74	7.72	7.73
	C ₃	12.66	12.67	12.69	12.72	12.69	7.68	7.66	7.65	7.62	7.65
W ₂	C ₁	7.30	7.32	7.39	7.33	7.34	7.83	7.83	7.84	7.86	7.84
	C ₂	10.27	10.32	10.28	10.30	10.29	7.85	7.85	7.85	7.88	7.86
	C ₃	12.60	12.56	12.61	12.68	12.61	7.86	7.83	7.78	7.78	7.81
W ₃	C ₁	7.04	7.07	7.02	7.00	7.06	7.88	7.82	7.86	7.96	7.88
	C ₂	10.04	10.01	9.96	9.92	9.98	7.89	7.91	7.96	7.96	7.93
	C ₃	12.51	12.46	12.50	12.36	12.46	7.90	7.97	7.97	8.00	7.96

The mean values of calculated SAR after plant harvesting increased from 3.65 up to 11.24 as shown in Fig. (2) with increasing sodium concentration in irrigation water used.

Fig. (2): Effect of salinity levels of different irrigation water on SAR and ESP of soil after harvesting

The difference in SAR values were pronounced with the third type of irrigation water which contains ratio of 1:2:6 from CaCl₂, MgCl₂ · 6H₂O and NaCl respectively. The calculated ESP was correlated with SAR values of irrigated soil after harvesting (Fig. 2). These results were in agreement with Amer *et al* (1997), they reported That the poor quality of irrigation water caused more soil salinity and alkalinity.

The results tabulated in Table (2) show that, the available N and P of the soil used after harvesting almost decreased with increasing salinity levels of irrigation water (available N from 99 to 67 mg/kg and available P from 21 to 15 mg/kg). Decreasing in available N may be due to ion exchange and increased N uptake by wheat plant under soil salinity, and the decrease in available P almost attribute to increasing soluble Ca and hence precipitated Ca – phosphate Compound (Mashali *et al.*,1995)

Table (2): Soil content of available N and P after wheat harvesting as affected by salinity levels and salt concentration of irrigation water.

Treatments		Available-N, mg N/kg soil					Available-P, mg P/kg soil				
Water quality	Salinity level	N ₀	N ₁	N ₂	N ₃	Mean	N ₀	N ₁	N ₂	N ₃	Mean
W ₀	C ₀	99	92	88	81	90	29	28	26	24	27
W ₁	C ₁	99	91	84	81	89	28	27	25	24	26
	C ₂	84	81	78	77	80	27	26	24	23	25
	C ₃	81	77	74	73	76	26	24	24	20	24
Mean		88	83	79	77	82	27	26	24	22	25
W ₂	C ₁	98	90	80	78	87	25	24	21	20	23
	C ₂	81	77	77	70	76	19	18	17	16	18
	C ₃	76	72	67	67	71	17	17	16	15	16
Mean		86	80	75	72	78	20	20	18	17	19
W ₃	C ₁	85	84	84	77	83	26	23	22	20	23
	C ₂	83	81	81	74	80	22	22	20	19	21
	C ₃	79	77	76	72	76	19	19	18	17	18
Mean		82	74	81	74	80	22	21	20	19	20

Wheat yield :

Figure (3) show that, the grain yield of wheat plant significantly reduced by raising the levels of water salinity where the percentage of this decrease was, 10, 20 and 30% when irrigation water had, 25,50 and 75 mg/L of salts and salts ratio was 1:1:1 compared with control treatment and without added-N. Salinity water generally have a bad effect on plant growth through its influence on several facets of plant metabolism like osmotic adjustment, ions uptake, protein, nucleic acids synthesis, enzyme activities and hormonal balance in plant (Abou El-Soud,1987)

On the other side, the addition of three units of N/ha increased grain yield by 300, 330 and 385% using C₁, C₂ and C₃ of W₁, respectively compared with it without added-N. These results indicate that the addition of N fertilizer under these conditions of water salinity rising plant tolerance to salinity and sodicity, where the grain content of Na decreased with increasing levels of added-N. Salinity level of water type had more effect on grain yield than the different ratio of salt concentration for water type. The mean values of grain yield were 10.2, 10.32 and 10.16 g/pot for W₁, W₂ and W₃, respectively compared with 11.25 g/pot for control treatment (W₀).

Fig. (3): Grain yield of wheat plant as affected by salinity levels of irrigation water and N levels.

Plant analysis shows that Na concentration of wheat grain increased as a function of salinity and SAR of irrigation water qualities and this lead to decreasing plant content of K,P and N (Fig. 4). Sodium concentration decreased from 0.14% to 0.06% when N added by 3 units using W₁ of irrigation water.

Fig. (4): The correlation between soluble Na⁺ in soil solution and wheat grain after plant harvesting

Conclusion

The present study indicated that, in case of, shortage supply by good quality of irrigation water the farmers can use the other sources of water which have less quality but this is under limited circumstances. Soil texture, composition of irrigation water, climatic region and growing plant are important factors to use the irrigation water. Addition of N fertilizer rise plant tolerance to salinity and sodicity effect of irrigation water, where nitrogen fertilizer increases plant growth and hence photosynthetic area, Under moderately and heavy textures of Egyptian soil, must be not use water salinity for irrigation more than 50 meq/L (5dS/m) where the decrease in grain weight

yield was economically increase under any addition of N fertilizer.

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